

MAHMUDKHOJA BEHBUDIY'S CONTRIBUTIONS TO PUBLISHING, JOURNALISM AND THEATRICAL PRACTICE

G.N. Akhmedov

Director of the Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy House Museum

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Abstract. *The article examines the Jadid movement, the socio-political processes that took place on the eve of the emergence of the progressive movement in Turkestan, and the enlighteners of the region. In particular, the author analyzes the activities of Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy, one of the largest representatives of the Samarkand Jadid movement, in the field of publishing, journalism and theater.*

Keywords: *jadidism, enlightenment, theater, journalism, progressive publishing, new-method schools, national thinking, intelligentsia, Turkestan, Turkestan autonomy.*

Introduction

As a progressive figure of his time, Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy was engaged in publishing, journalism and theater, striving to convey the ideas of Jadidism to the people through newspapers and magazines, as well as stage productions. To this end, he deeply studied foreign experience and began to work on its basis. It is known that at that time publishing and theater were very developed not only in Europe, but also in many Asian countries.

Historical research shows that the first newspaper that Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy read was "Tarjiman". In addition, he regularly read "Hayot" by Alimardanbek Tanchibayev, published in Baku, "Irshod" by Akhmed Agayev, "Ulfat" by Abdurashid Ibrohimov, published in St. Petersburg, the newspaper "Vakt" by Fatih Karimov, published in Orenburg, "Shu'ro" by Muhammad Shokir and Muhammad Zakir, the magazines "Din va maishat" by Muhammad Vali Husaynov, the newspapers "Chehranamo" and "Siroj ul akhbor afgoniya", published in Iran and Afghanistan. In addition, during his travels he visited printing houses in different cities. Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy had his own printing house.

There is no exact information about when this printing house, called "Nashriyoti Behbudiy", was opened and where the printing equipment was purchased. Probably, it was put into operation around the same year as the library. The printing house published for the first time a map of Turkestan, Bukhara and Khiva compiled by Behbudiy in Turkish, textbooks, teaching aids, the drama "Padarkush" and Fitrat's poem "Hind Sayyohi Kisassi", translated into Russian. Behbudiy published and distributed these books at his own expense. The publishing house existed until 1915, that is, until the cessation of the activity of the magazine "Oyina".

On February 14, 1913, Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy wrote a petition to the military governor of the Samarkand region with a request for permission to publish the newspaper, attaching to it a table of contents indicating the areas of activity of the newspaper:

- Government orders;
- Main articles;
- Foreign news;

- Domestic news;
- News;
- Local and trade chronicle of the country;
- News of the Russian and foreign press;
- Agriculture;
- Feuilleton, literary and scientific department;
- Correspondents and private telegrams;
- Court reports of people's judges of the entire empire and, in particular, judges;
- Theater;
- Announcements;
- Answers from the office;
- Design and illustrations;
- Mixture.

After the table of contents, Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy also noted the purpose of publishing the newspaper. Although this publication was intended to spread Russian culture and European science among the population of Turkestan and bring Muslims closer to Russians, This "goal" was not set in any issue of the newspaper.

The newspaper "Samarkand" was published in Samarkand twice a week in Uzbek, Persian and Russian languages from April 15, 1913 with a circulation of 400-600 copies. The newspaper published articles and poems predicting the development of Turkestan and calling for social reforms. The newspaper also covered the activities of newspapers in Europe and the USA and their readers. Articles by such Jadids as Haji Muin, Munavvarkori, Fitrat, Kamii, Saidrizo Alizade, Siddiqiy Adjzii, Nusratilla Kudratilla oglu (Milliy) and Rojii were published.

The newspaper was subscribed mainly to the Jadids of Turkestan. One of them, Vadud Mahmud, proudly recalls his subscription to the newspaper: "It was when I was working as a teacher's assistant (halfa) at the Muallim Shakuriy School. One day they took me with them to the editorial office of this newspaper. I still remember it. We entered the new building on Reshitnikov Street. A large building. The editor of the newspaper, Behbudiy, was sitting at the table wearing glasses. On one side sat the newspaper's translator, Saidrizo Saidzoda, and on the other, the newspaper distributor. Haji Muin Shukrullo oglu was busy writing ads. It was here that we subscribed to the newspaper and returned. This event became important in my life. After all, in those days, who knows how many people in a big city like Samarkand subscribed to the newspaper and became sellers. A special postman delivered the newspaper, which was published two or three times a week. I was among them. "I was, and it was a great honor for me".

As a result of constant pressure from the government and propaganda among the population, based on antiquity, that the newspaper's readers were infidels, the number of subscribers to the Samarkand newspaper dropped sharply. According to the memoirs of Vadud Mahmud, "in Samarkand alone, the circulation barely reached a hundred copies". Due to financial difficulties and constant censorship, Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy was forced to stop publishing the newspaper after the 44th issue. Upon learning of this, the Kokand Jadids Akobir Shomansur oglu and Mirzohid Okiliy expressed their willingness to send 200 subscription sheets with a donation of 500 soums to ensure the continuity of the newspaper's publication. Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy stated that he would not be able to continue publishing the newspaper for long through donations and subscriptions, and refused the donation. On September 17, 1913, the last, 45th issue of the one-page newspaper "Samarkand" was published. At that time, Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy had

already begun publishing the magazine "Oyina". He wrote a petition to the military governor of the Samarkand region for permission to open a magazine and presented him with the contents of the magazine:

- Government orders;
- Main article;
- Review of foreign events;
- Review of domestic events;
- News;
- General information about the local and commercial life of the country;
- Review of the Russian and foreign press;
- Agriculture;
- Feuilleton, literary and scientific section;
- Intelligence and private telegrams;
- Court reports of people's judges of the entire empire and judges in particular;
- Theater;
- Announcements;
- Responses from the chancery;
- Decorations and illustrations;
- Satire and miscellaneous.

The Printing Department issued Certificate No. 11576 for the publication of the magazine on June 8, and its first issue was published on August 20, 1913. As Abdullah Avloni said: "This magazine was the first and best of the magazines published before the publication of Oyina". Behbudiy named the magazine "Mirot" (Arabic), "Kozgu" (Uzbek), "Oyina" (Tajik) and "Zerkalo" (Russian) in four languages. Articles were accepted and published in Uzbek and Tajik. Advertisements and announcements were placed in the magazine in Russian. The first issue of the magazine consisted of 24 pages, and the second issue was published 2 months later. Starting from the second issue, the magazine was published continuously, and 52 issues were received by subscribers.

Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy appealed to the intelligentsia of the country with a request to write articles for the magazine. Articles and poems by Abdurauf Fitrat, Siddiqi, Haji Muin, Akobir Shomansur, Muhammad Said, Saidrizo Alizoda, Saidahmad Wasli, Tavallo, Sadridin Ainiya, Hakim Bukhari, Niyoziya Rajabzoda contributed to the popularity of "Oyina". The publication also served as a testing ground for young writers, future literary figures and educators. The articles in the magazine covered political, economic, social, cultural and religious topics.

The best articles by Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy were published in the Oyina magazine. In particular, "We Need Not Two, but Four Languages" (issue 1), "Small Debt, Property Credit" (issue 1), "Project-Project" (issues 9-11), "Who Will Reform the Nation?" (issue 12), "Emergency Takfir" (issue 12), "Hollar va Ishar" (issue 13), "Oh, the Banks Have Ruined Us" (issue 19), "Appeal to the Youth" (issue 21), "Is the Theater Not Worth It?" (issue 29), "Criticism is a matter of choice" (issue 31), "The harm of alcoholism" (issue 36), "We need the history of Turkestan" (issue 38), "We need patriotism" (issue 43), "Conversation with His Holiness Ismailbek" (issue 49), "The history of Ismailbek" (issue 50), "Sherdor Madrasah" (issue 1), "Ulugbek Observatory" (issues 3-9), "History and Geography" (issues 27-28), "Travel Memories" (issues 34-53), "The Sun" (issues 49-51) and other analytical articles and journalistic works testify to our opinion..

The editor of the official organ of the Turkestan Governorate General, the Turkestan Regional Gazette, repeatedly speaks out against articles published in the republican journal. The Oyina newspaper also responds to the newspaper's statements. For example, in the Turkestan Regional Gazette, Nikolai Ostroumov claims that the population of Turkestan should be called "Sarts." Understanding that the word "Sart" is used in a derogatory sense, Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy gives a reasoned response in the article "The Word Sart Is Unknown" in issues 22–26 of the Oyina magazine in 1914.

The activities of the Oyina magazine were under constant control of special government agencies. The National Archives of Uzbekistan contain letter No. 100 dated August 19, 1914, signed by the Chief of Staff of the Turkestan Military District, sent to the military governor of the Samarkand region. Its content boils down to the fact that during the First World War, "in connection with the possibility of articles appearing in the local press that contradict the interests of Russia," the Turkestan military censorship instructed Staff Captain Otayev to monitor publications in Samarkand. The editor-in-chief was instructed to send an excerpt (reprint) from the Oyina magazine for proofreading two days before the magazine was published. Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy was summoned to the military district and signed this "secret letter" with the words: "I have read and taken note." Before leaving for Hajj, Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy temporarily handed over the editorial office of the newspaper "Oyina" to Saidrizo Alizoda. On May 3, 1914, the military governor issued Saidrizo Alizoda a certificate for the temporary performance of the duties of the editor.

The content of the magazine "Oyina" is based on the protection of national interests. From the first to the last issue, special attention is paid to the history of Turkestan and the legacy of great thinkers. For example, on the first page of the first issue there is a majestic photograph of the Sherdor Madrasah and an editorial article "Turkistan", and then there is the history of the Sherdor Madrasah.

Haji Muin writes the following about the magazine: "Oyina" served well in awakening the people... "Oyina" spread from Turkestan to Tatarstan, the Caucasus, Afghanistan, Iran, Turkey and Egypt and was widely read everywhere".

By 1915, the activities of the Oyina magazine were completely suspended. Although the last, 16th issue of 1915, reported: "...Our editor and publisher suffered from nervous, leg and stomach diseases, and doctors advised him to treat them with salt mines and mineral waters in Turkestan, so our editor was forced to undergo a course of treatment and rest. Due to the absence of the editor of Oyina, Oyina was forced to come out only on August 1 or September 1, that is, within one or two months. If God willing, the 17th issue of Oyina will probably come out on September 1, since this is much later..." although the reason for the cessation of the magazine's activities is said to be Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy's health problems, in fact, constant pressure and censorship by the occupation government put an end to its existence.

Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy was one of the best publicists of his time. His articles can be divided into two groups by period. If the articles written before February 1917 are dominated by articles devoted to issues of education and economics, then the articles written from February 1917 to 1919 widely cover political and social processes.

Behbudiy published his publicistic articles in 18 newspapers in Turkestan, the Caucasus, Crimea and Tatarstan. These include national newspapers such as Turkiston Viloyatin Gazeti, Tarakki, Tujor, Khurshid, Shuhrat, Osiyo, Turon, Hurriyat, Najot, Mehnatkashlar Tovuz, Ulug Turkistan, as well as foreign newspapers such as Tarjiman, Waqt, Shu'ro, Ulfat, Irshod, Toza

Hayot. Haji Muin stated that "About two hundred articles by Behbudiy were published in these 18 newspapers and magazines, which, if collected together, would make up a book of 500-600 pages. Most of Behbudiy's articles published in these newspapers and magazines were written on important topics, have not become outdated, and are still useful words for us today".

Behbudiy's journalistic activity began in 1903 with the publication of an article in the official organ of the Turkestan Governor-General "Turkiston Viloyatin Gazeti". In almost all the articles published in this publication, he wrote "Turkiston" instead of "Turkiston Viloyatin Gazeti". The purpose of this writing was not to shorten the name of the newspaper, but to remind people that this was not a province, but a large state, and to introduce this idea into the consciousness of the people.

In his first article, entitled "Letter from Samarkand", he criticized Samarkand judges for issuing decisions in absentia and emphasized the need to reform the industry. The author encouraged readers to study the laws, regulations, and procedures of the colonial government, citing the procedure for summoning, sending a subpoena, and sample receipts for receiving a subpoena.

In the article "On the Benefits of Knowledge," he sharply criticized the outdated teaching methods in schools and madrassas. He emphasized that young people who do not receive the necessary knowledge even after 8-10 years of study bring more harm to society than good, and called on Turkestan scholars to eliminate this problem. He taught that ignorance leads to ignorance. Behbudiy did not simply pay attention to the "primitive education" of the youth. The writer, whose ultimate goal was to achieve independence through education, also put on the agenda the issue of training personnel capable of becoming deputies of the State Duma, lawyers in courts and defending the national interests of their people, as well as qualified specialists in all areas of science and culture, the national economy.

He ended his article entitled "A Nation in Need" with the following words: "If the rich from all over Turkestan gave a thousand sums for ten years, a religious and modern "boarding school" for 25 children would be built in Tashkent, 5 excellent schools with evening and daytime education, and 50 children would study annually in state schools. In ten years you would have ... 200 engineers, doctors, lawyers, teachers, technicians, modern traders, by God (if God willing) ... and they would count us among the people of our time and enter the civil service. "They would serve us together with the Russians for our good interests (unification). This is what our nation expects from the rich, and not from constant marriages that ruin the people. Oh, do we have enough permanent rich people to understand these words?".

In his article "On Elections," he criticized bribery in appointments to positions and posts. He said that it was harmful to the people that governors, unable to read or write, received 1,000-2,000 coins and were appointed judges, volost and other officials, and that, having taken office, they performed their duties for bribes. He proposed electing scholars from the people.

In addition to editing the newspaper "Samarkand", Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy also published his own articles. In the article "How Nations Develop" he presented data on developed countries and came to the conclusion that the main reason for development is attention to science. He noted that reforming schools and madrassas is a requirement of the times: "If today we do not reform schools and madrassas, that is, do not reform the nation, then in a century religion will collapse, and the responsibility for its solution will fall on the shoulders of contemporaries. In order to get rid of this responsibility, it is necessary to encourage the nation to engage in religious and secular science".

Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy also spoke in the newspaper "Tujor". In the 10th and 11th issues of the newspaper for 1907, an article "Islohi tahsil" was published, in which he emphasized the need for school reform and expressed regret over the indifference of domestic scientists to these processes.

In the book by Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy "General Geography" in the section "Sages of Turkestan" there is information about our great thinkers. In particular, you can read the following thoughts about Ibn Sina: "Sheikhurai Ibn Sina Abu Ali - dictionary, logic, geography, music, ethics, chemistry, natural science, wisdom, medicine, astrology, systematized more than a hundred books, which is the first of the Muslim rulers. Most of his books were translated into European languages, and the French call him "Avicenna". He died in 428".

The book includes a list of 29 scientists who lived and worked in the Turanian lands, such as Abu Nasr Farabi, Khoja Fakhriddin, Bahriddin Samarkand, Abdurahmon Khorezmi, Abu Ibrahim Koragoni, Sharif Khorezmi, Abu Jafar Khorezmi, Muhammad Chagmini, Ahmad Fergani, Ali Kushchi Samarkand, Mirzo Ulugbek, Muhammad Khojandi, Abu Rayhan Khorezmi, Abu Said Somoni, as well as their scientific works. The newspaper "Samarkand" and the magazine "Oyina", not limited to the information presented in the book, also sought to reveal the life and work of great thinkers. For example, an article about Mirzo Ulugbek was published in the newspaper "Samarkand" on April 30, 1913.

Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy also wrote a series of articles in the newspaper "Samarkand" about the situation and state of affairs in Turkey. In his articles, he emphasized that he had lived in Turkey for some time during the Hajj pilgrimage and his boundless respect for the Ottoman Empire. Perhaps the main reason for this is that the Ottoman Empire was the only independent state in the Turkic world, and the majority of its population were Muslims. It was not without reason that he devoted an editorial to Turkey in the first issue of the Samarkand newspaper. Considering that the Russian Empire had always pursued a hostile policy towards the Ottoman Empire, the content of the articles shows that he tried to convey information and news about this state to readers very carefully.

In the articles of Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy, published after the February events of 1917, political topics prevailed. In particular, in his articles in the newspaper "Najot" he put forward the following ideas: "The missionaries and people of the old and tyrannical government, who wanted us to disappear and perish, and our sacred Sharia to be excluded from the government, issued such laws, for example, a law was passed that "every Turkestan citizen who has reached the age of 25 can be a judge and a volost". This law helped us to choose illiterate and uneducated judges with money and bribes". Behbudiy noted that not only judges and volost elders, but also inexperienced and uneducated people were appointed to the positions of madrasah teachers. This weakened the incentive for science and contributed to the decline of scientists. Scientists were left without work. In these reflections, he tried to reveal the essence of the colonial policy of the Russian Empire in Turkestan. He called on the people to unite, fight for freedom, independence and independence.

Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy's articles on political and social issues were also published in the newspaper "Khurriyat". In particular, in the article "The Bukhara Events and the Fight against Slander," he provides information about his participation in a meeting dedicated to the publication of a manifesto signed by the Emir of Bukhara about the demonstration of the Bukhara Jadids and its suppression.

In his "Honest Address to the Honorable Samarkandians," he emphasized the need to overcome the differences between the new and old Jadids of Samarkand in the freedom movement.

In this article, Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy emphasizes that he has been fighting for development for 20 years and calls on the youth to unite, measure ten times and cut once: "Throw this idea out of your minds, it is difficult for you to develop alone. Perhaps you will develop together with your entire city and nation. I have also been working for twenty years so that development can take place. You also know that development cannot and will not take place with ten or twenty people".

In his article "Bayoni Haqiqat", Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy develops the above ideas, paying special attention to the issues of national freedom and national statehood: "It should be known: rights are taken, not given. The people of each nation and country receive their rights, religious and political, from others through actions and alliances". The thinker, who believed in the promises of the Provisional Government, advocated taking Russia into account in political and economic matters and for joint actions, but put forward the idea of independent management of internal affairs and the creation of its own parliament.

When the Turkestan Autonomy was formed on November 27, 1917, the people, unaccustomed to living independently, were at a loss. Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy tried to calm them down and explain the essence of autonomy. He claims that the concept of autonomy did not arise today, and efforts to create it began in April 1917.

It should be noted here that attempts to provoke conflicts between Uzbeks and Kazakhs, the desire of Kazakhs to create a separate autonomy also worried Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy, and in the issue of the newspaper "Khurriyat" of January 26, 1918, he published "An Open Letter to Our Kazakh Brothers": "Fathers! Know that autonomy has now been declared for all the peoples of Turkestan, and, you know, "The right is taken, not given!" That is, the children of Turkestan themselves will unite and enthusiastically gain "autonomy", of course, others will not give it. If others can, they will not. If we do nothing, and the peoples of Turkestan do not unite and do not strive for autonomy, then they will certainly destroy our current autonomy on paper, this is certainly true, and no one can disagree with this word.

My light, let's unite! You see, today's Russians are uniting. Now is the time to unite. If you split, if the Turkmen relatives... divided, the Turks of Turkestan will be divided into three parts, and not all will have a chance for autonomy.

Contrary to Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy's ideas about autonomy without fear and panic, the Turkestan autonomy is flooded with blood. This plunges the thinker into deep depression, and for some time he does not make statements in the press. But at this time, Turkestan faced another problem - hunger. In addition, the Bolsheviks, using the method of "pulling a stick out of the ground", put on the agenda the issue of conscripting the population of Turkestan, creating a "national army" and sending it to fight the militarists who were fighting for the freedom of the Motherland. Realizing the vile intentions of the Soviet government, the father of the Turkestan Jadids, Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy, was one of the first to present his views on the issue of military service to the government.

When Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy arrived in Tashkent on July 16, 1918 to resolve issues related to grain in Samarkand, the chairman of the Turkestan government, Ivan Tobolin met with him and discussed with him the issues of grain, recruitment of soldiers, war compensation, land and water. Based on his many years of experience, Ivan Tobolin told him that "at least a little attention and observation is needed for the current situation of the internal and external enemies of Turkestan, for the state of the people, their spirituality, beliefs and way of life," and presented his proposals. Two of his proposals concerned the military sphere, the first of which was the question of universal military service. Behbudiy expressed the opinion that the Turkestanis were

not ready for this, that until the population had acquired skills and the situation changed, universal military service should not be carried out, and that young volunteers should be recruited based on their family circumstances.

Secondly, the contribution was a war tax, and Behbudiy opposed the imposition of this tax on the people of Turkestan, especially on the people of Samarkand, who were suffering from famine: "Famine reigned throughout Turkestan, especially in Samarkand, and although there were fewer rich people in Samarkand than in other places, the Russians, Jews and Muslims gave up to eight yuns of national contribution and up to three million yuns of famine tax in Samarkand alone... Conclusion: in any case, it would be better if the contribution from Samarkand was no longer collected. Because now life and politics demand peace. The people are also tired and nervous from hunger, high prices and similar privations. If money is needed, it can be collected in other ways, including through taxes".

Ivan Tobolin promised to recruit soldiers voluntarily in Samarkand and not to collect military fees any more, and to develop measures for this. In order to use Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy in his own interests, he offered him the post of Minister of Education of Samarkand. After working in this position for some time, the people could not accept the education system and resigned, which he reported in the article "Thank you and respect".

Over the course of 15 years, the great thinker published more than 200 articles and reports in more than ten newspapers and magazines. The articles were written in simple and accessible language, analyzing the political, economic, social and cultural problems of Turkestan.

Also worthy of attention is the theatrical activity of Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy. In 1911, he wrote the drama "Padarkush" for the theater. Having received permission from the Tiflis censorship with the inscription on the cover of the book "Dedicated to the anniversary of the Battle of Borodino and the liberation of Russia from French occupation", he published it in 1913. In 1914, the scientist founded the National Theater to inspire people to progress, showing on stage the vices, shortcomings and ignorance of public life.

The author called the drama "Padarkush" a "national tragedy", consisting of three acts and four scenes, compact in volume, extremely simple and understandable in content. Behbudiy drew the viewer's attention to the "situation of an uneducated child", showing the tragic fate of a child who, without going to school, lived comfortably thanks to the money of his rich father. "Padarkush" was first staged on January 15, 1914 in Samarkand, and on February 27, 1914 in Tashkent. Before the performance, Munavvarkori Abdurashidkhanov gives a speech about the role of theater in society: "... The true meaning of theater is a house of learning or a school for great people. The theater stage is like a house with windows on all sides, where everyone, entering it, sees their beauty and ugliness, shortcomings and vices and learns from them. And on this stage he tries to atone for the low customs and corrupt morals that are offensive to him".

The second performance of Padarkush in Samarkand took place on May 7, 1914. The ticket sales raised 384 sums 50 tyis, of which 184 sums 50 tyis went towards organizing the performance. Of the remaining 200 sums, 110 sums were used to reform schools: 35 sums went to the school founded by Bozoramin Orinjoja in Dzhambay, 15 sums to the Bogishamol school, 15 sums to the Mullah Jorabay school in the village of Bukhori, 25 sums to the Muslim students of the City School, and 35 sums to the Abdukadir Shakuri school. Obviously, all the income was spent on educational work.

The Turon troupe toured the Fergana Valley with this performance in 1914–1916. This play was performed even during the years of pogroms that shook Turkestan. On the one hand, it

inspired the people to the path of enlightenment and progress, on the other, it served the formation and development of a truly Uzbek theater and drama. However, there were those who called the theater blasphemy. Said Akhmad Vasli, Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy's closest friend and comrade-in-arms in the reform of schools and madrassas, called the theater heresy, he calls it haram.. Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy did not treat Vasli as rudely as he did and wrote the following reply: "Let us move on to the issue of theatre. The theatre of today is an innovation. They say "innovation" because the innovations that appeared after the Prophet are divided into two parts: if they benefit the religion and the nation, they are called "good innovations." If they harm the religion and the nation, they are called "sinful innovations".

As Vasli noted, the theater was not banned. It was a place of example, advice, education and spirituality. Behind the excessive expenses on weddings, the main themes for theatrical productions were the fates of ruined people, the violation of women's rights, drug addiction, debauchery and greed.

Conclusion

In short, Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy studied the experience of organizing newspapers and magazines for 10 years. Although this did not last long, he founded the newspaper "Samarkand" and the magazine "Oyina". In this work, he observed with his own eyes the activities of editors from the Caucasus, India, Egypt and Turkey. In addition to editorial work, he also worked fruitfully in the field of journalism. He published more than 200 articles in 18 types of newspapers and magazines.

He decided to show himself the shortcomings of Turkestan society, show the ways to return from this path and achieve progress through the theater and laid the foundation for this. The drama "Padarkush", written by him for staging on the theater stage, gained popularity.

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